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THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON THE CREATION OF MULTIMEDIA CONTENT

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Abstract

Within the project "Use of Artificial Intelligence (ChatGPT) in the Course of Management and Organisation of Media Production," part of the Media and Journalism higher education programme, we conducted a study to assess the possibilities offered by ChatGPT in the production of multimedia content. Students, as part of the study process, created two products: a professional manual presenting the establishment, structuring, and management of an organisation within a specific area of media production, and a shorter audiovisual (AV) product. The research monitored the flow of processes and explored students' opinions pertaining to the role of artificial intelligence in the study and implementation process. The results are of value in planning the next steps in integrating artificial intelligence into the academic and production processes.

Keywords: ChatGPT, artificial intelligence, media, media production, education, higher education

Introduction

With the emergence of the free ChatGPT platform in 2022, artificial intelligence became widely accessible and rapidly spread, particularly among the younger generation and within educational systems worldwide. Among the early adopters were higher education institutions focusing on media production. Industry experts, especially those in the film industry and other artistic professions, quickly recognised the significance and potential risks of artificial intelligence. In 2023, they organised a strike with the intention of reducing the use of AI in the film industry and prevent potential decreases in pay and employment. The five-month strike concluded in September 2023, with the main achievement being the assurance

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that the demand for creative individuals using AI would not diminish, and their payment for similar products would not be lower, even though a significant portion of the work was done by AI (Anguiano D., Beckett L., 2023). The contract is valid for three years, during which many changes are likely to occur that will impact media production. Due to student interest, we conducted a study to explore the ways in which ChatGPT could be meaningfully integrated into the educational process, specifically in the project work in which students create multimedia products.

In English, ChatGPT stands for "Chat Generative Pre-trained Transformer." It is a model based on Transformer technology, designed for generating text and responding to natural language questions (ChatGPT, 2023).

UNESCO has warned that the adoption of ChatGPT in schools is happening too rapidly, without sufficient checks, rules, or regulations. The education sector is largely unprepared for the ethical and pedagogical integration of these rapidly evolving tools. A global UNESCO survey of over 450 schools and universities revealed that fewer than 10% have institutional policies and/or formal guidance regarding the use of generative AI applications, primarily due to the lack of appropriate national regulations.

The publication also includes guidelines for regulating artificial intelligence in education (page 8), published by UNESCO on September 7, 2023. This document recommends that the minimum age at which students may use AI should be 13 and emphasises the need for ethical use, data protection, privacy considerations, and teacher education. One significant challenge is that current ChatGPT models are trained using data from online users, reflecting the values and prevailing social norms of the global north.

Upon reviewing sources, we found that ChatGPT is highly interactive, responsive, fast, and popular, providing instant answers to various questions from different fields. For students, it is crucial that ChatGPT includes a feature for quickly generating essays (Biswas, 2023). Many universities and researchers are exploring ways to conduct reviews, exams, and tests to prevent plagiarism and cheating (Shir, 2023).

Furthermore, ChatGPT can answer complex professional questions, understand cultural contexts, and edit, proofread, and translate academic essays (Lecler et al., 2023). The use of ChatGPT offers equal opportunities to students, regardless of their location or financial status (Baidoo and Ansah, 2023).

ChatGPT appears to be a revolutionary tool, always available and either free or very affordable, aiding students in completing tasks and achieving good results effortlessly (Rudolph et al., 2023). Its use allows for personalised, reliable, and specialised guidance in preparing various tasks, such as essays, poems, programming code, recipes, instructions, etc., in a short amount of time with considerably less effort. In the field of media, ChatGPT is beneficial for developing ideas, stories, headlines, synopses, books, and scripts, including shooting scripts.

Academic integrity expert Sarah Elaine Eaton argues that, instead of preventing the use of tools like ChatGPT, we should critically evaluate how we implement their usage and assessment. Traditional methods such as online exams, homework writing, and web-based tests are being reevaluated and replaced with non-text products, skill development, and multimodal tests, exams, and assignments in the classroom. Multimodal tests involve multiple forms of expression, combining text, images, sound, video, etc., encouraging diverse ways of demonstrating knowledge.

The central idea from Ben Williamson, the author of the introductory article in the publication "Education in the Age of Artificial Intelligence," is that the use of artificial intelligence in education must be subject to control and independent assessments for schools to maintain their mission of developing critical thinking and shaping future citizens (Education in the Age of Artificial Intelligence, 2023, p. 6).

The use of artificial intelligence, particularly ChatGPT, poses a significant challenge for both teachers and students. The effects are rapid, extensive, and diverse, with much still undefined and untested, requiring careful consideration when incorporating the possibilities offered by AI into teaching. Those introducing ChatGPT into education must be aware that this is the first, free, most straightforward, basic use of AI for text preparation. Many more powerful applications and possibilities, particularly in various professional fields, are already available, significantly influencing both education and professional multimedia production.

The integration of ChatGPT into the study programme is challenging and involves considerable responsibility, given the limited research and practical experience. While ChatGPT is being cautiously introduced into educational institutions for specific subjects or activities, students are already using it extensively.

The lack of comprehensive studies comparing study processes and learning outcomes in different groups over an extended period is

problematic. The widespread use of AI only became possible with the free ChatGPT programme in 2023.

In the initial research, we attempted to determine how to sensibly and rationally integrate AI (specifically the free ChatGPT programme) into the educational process for the subject "Management and Organisation of Media Production" in the Media and Journalism programme at FUDŠ, Ljubljana, especially in the preparation of specific products (written materials and AV products).

We focused on the functions crucial for data acquisition and processing within ChatGPT. While acknowledging certain flaws and challenges in ChatGPT, such as algorithmic choices, biased data, mechanical language, and often inadequate translations, we aim to contribute modestly to understanding the integration of ChatGPT into the educational process. Our findings may be useful in planning the next academic year's subject and in the broader activities of the faculty, aligning with its vision and strategy for AI integration.

Purpose and objectives of the research

The research also attempted to assess how the use of ChatGPT influences the process of producing media products by students. As we conducted the study and educational process with only one group of 36 students, we compared some results with those of a group using the same programme but without ChatGPT in the previous academic year. In other comparisons, we considered that this was the only subject in which students systematically used ChatGPT.

Research questions and hypotheses

We formulated a research question and two hypotheses, preparing a survey for each research question.

Research Question: What is the impact of artificial intelligence (ChatGPT) on student performance in creating materials: a professional manual and a short film?

Hypothesis 1: Students using ChatGPT in creating a professional manual will achieve better results in a shorter time compared to those who do not use this tool.

Hypothesis 2: Students using ChatGPT in creating an AV product will produce a more creative product than those without ChatGPT.

Methods

We employed a qualitative research method to gather data through the review and analysis of sources, surveys among students, and interviews with both students and experts regarding the research outcomes. Additionally, we referred to the manual "Fundamentals of Research Work in Multimedia Production" (Zakrajšek, 2021).

As a preparation for the research, we had to appropriately design the course programme for the Management and Organisation of Media Production, as well as the teaching approach. This was based on the insights and solutions derived from the review and analysis of literature and sources, as well as discussions with experts and students.

The research involved 29 female students and 7 male students from the second year, totaling 36 individuals who completed the survey and participated in presenting their projects, discussing the survey results.

Research preparation and student engagement

Within the course on Management and Organisation of Media Production, we conducted a brief but systematic training session on the use of the free ChatGPT programme, focusing on text and project preparation. We utilised the free version of ChatGPT, which doesn't access the latest web sources, requiring students to search for information online and in libraries.

To understand the research results, it is crucial to note that we did not systematically acquaint students with the creative applications of ChatGPT, which offers numerous possibilities using creativity techniques.

Students, using the user interface, performed various exercises and also developed two projects:

- A professional manual on the management and organisation of media production in their chosen field. Students worked individually or in groups of two or three, depending on their preference.
- A 1.5-minute film, shot in a single frame on a specific topic. Students formed and worked in groups of five, thereby experiencing project teamwork.

Professional Manual on media production management and organisation

In the professional manual, students had to present the establishment, management, and organisation of a company in their chosen field of interest. They began by searching for at least three similar materials in Slovenian and foreign languages through online platforms. Based on ChatGPT's suggestions, students prepared a proposed title, outlines, and a content index. The proposed material was reviewed, and adjustments were made collaboratively.

Emphasis was placed on ChatGPT-generated questions (what, where, why, how much, where to, with whom...) and evaluating the answers in accordance with research methodology principles. Subsequently, the students, considering the structure of similar materials, prepared coordinated content outlines and an index for the manual. The structure had to align with the lecture content so that students could supplement the material after each session, confirming their understanding through mandatory assignments. Drafts were reviewed, and feedback was provided, with ChatGPT and various sources assisting in resolving dilemmas and questions. Students also conducted interviews with experts from relevant organisations, enhancing their understanding and validating the information obtained from artificial intelligence.

Preparation of AV product: 1.5 - minute film

As a collaborative project, students planned and produced a 1.5-minute film shot in a single frame, with only subsequent audio processing allowed. The theme was "Evoking fear among people during the day." Each group of five students included individuals with skills in video, audio, writing, and graphic design. ChatGPT was utilised at all stages of the project, from brainstorming titles, preparing synopses, scripts, and storyboards, to planning and executing the production.

A particular focus of this project was on assessing the impacts on people and the environment and analysing risks. Positive evaluation of the project required the product's publication on YouTube, achieving at least 100 views, and receiving positive feedback during the final presentation, during which students also assessed each other's projects and proposed improvements.

Eight films and eight posters were created, with all the films achieving over 100 views on YouTube. The most viewed reached over 500 views. Posters were displayed in the school's lecture hall. For many students, this marked their first publicly shared product, with some showing enthusiasm and a talent for performance.

Review and study of sources

In the research, the method of reviewing and studying sources was crucial in almost all phases. A systematic literature review indicated a substantial number of hits in databases related to keywords such as AI, Artificial Intelligence, and education. However, the specific combination of keywords in the narrower field of AI related to media and education was less explored. This might be attributed to

ChatGPT's recent emergence and the initial focus on safety and risks, with in-depth research expected as ChatGPT becomes systematically integrated into study programmes.

Surveys, interviews, and conversations

In addition to source and literature reviews, surveys, interviews, and conversational methods were primarily employed.

Surveys

Various types of questions were used in the surveys, reflecting the educational process as students familiarised themselves with different question types and data processing issues. Four types of questions were utilised:

- Open-ended questions, allowing free-form responses, were used when seeking specific information from respondents.
- Closed-ended questions, offering predetermined answers for selection or evaluation, were employed to gather precise data for the research.
- Likert scale questions, featuring uniformly spaced response options, enabled respondents to rank their assessments numerically or with words.
- Importance-ranking questions, requiring respondents to rank items by importance.

Interviews

Interviews, as a qualitative data collection method, were directed towards individuals and small groups, allowing in-depth data acquisition and discussion of various perspectives, beliefs, and dilemmas.

In our research, direct interviews or conversations through platforms like Zoom were conducted with students and individuals involved in projects, addressing dilemmas, answering questions, and providing guidance for future work.

RESULTS

The responses to the survey related to the research question are presented.

Research Question: What is the impact of artificial intelligence (ChatGPT) on student success in creating materials: a professional manual and a short film?

The survey for the research question included three closed-ended questions, three open-ended questions, three Likert scale questions,

and three importance ranking questions. For each task, the question, result, and a brief comment are provided.

Closed-ended Questions:

1. Do you think that the inclusion of artificial intelligence makes the process of creating professional manuals and short films easier or more difficult?

N	Option	Number of responses	%
1	Easier	34	94.4
2	More difficult	1	2.8
3	Don't know/Do not wish to answer	1	2.8

Comment: *The majority, 94.4% of students, believe that the inclusion of artificial intelligence makes the process of creating professional manuals and short films easier.*

2. How much time did you spend preparing the manual using artificial intelligence compared to the traditional approach?

N	Option	Number of responses	%
1	Less time	31	86.1 %
2	About the same time	5	13.9 %
3	More time	-	-
4	Cannot estimate	-	-

Comment: *86.1% of students reported that they spent less time using AI for manual preparation compared to the traditional approach.*

3. Do you think that using artificial intelligence helped you in better organising and managing media projects?

N	Option	Number of responses	%
1	Yes	20	55.5
2	No	10	27.8
3	Don't know/Do not wish to answer	6	16.7

Comment: *55.5% of students believe that AI helped them in better organising and managing media projects, while 27.8% think there was no such assistance, and 16.7% did not know or did not wish to answer.*

Open-ended Questions:

4. How would you describe your experience collaborating with artificial intelligence in creating professional manuals and short films? Different degrees of usefulness for different projects: Artificial intelligence (ChatGPT) proved useful in creating professional manuals, aiding in quick information gathering and processing. However, its usefulness in creating short films varied. Some noticed benefits, while others believed the creative process in film relied more on human imagination.

Increased efficiency and speed: The majority agreed that using AI contributed to faster work and greater efficiency in content creation. Manuals were created more quickly, information was more accessible, and ideas emerged faster.

Significance for manuals: Most positive experiences were related to creating professional manuals. AI provided information, assisted in content organisation, and facilitated the writing process.

Limited creative role in films: Despite overall positivity, opinions on the usefulness of AI in creating short films differed. Some felt AI did not significantly contribute to the creative process, and the group's ideas were better.

Positive impact on collaboration and communication: Some respondents noted that collaboration was eased with AI, as everyone better understood and achieved goals more quickly. This indicates a positive impact on teamwork and communication. Overall, the gathered information suggests that AI can play a crucial role in the faster and more efficient creation of professional manuals, while its role in creating short films depends on the nature of the creative process and the preferences of the participants.

Summary: Artificial intelligence (ChatGPT) has proven beneficial in rapidly creating professional manuals, enhancing efficiency and speed of work, and facilitating collaboration and communication within groups. However, its utility in creating short films varies, with some recognising benefits while others believe the creative process in filmmaking is more dependent on human imagination.

5. What specific challenges did you experience when using artificial intelligence in projects within the course?

Difficulty understanding and responding: Several respondents highlighted challenges in understanding and responding to AI, as it sometimes responded too broadly, incorrectly, or repeated information, making it difficult to obtain specific data.

Grammatical and content errors: Many noticed grammatical errors and oddly written information. Challenges included incorrect information, inappropriate grammar, and answers in Croatian instead of Slovenian.

Challenges in citing sources: Some mentioned challenges in citing sources, as AI could not precisely specify the source of information. This was crucial for projects requiring source citation in manuals.

Limited usefulness for specific cases: Some expressed the unreliability of AI in specific cases, as it sometimes fabricated information and did not accurately cite sources. They also faced challenges in obtaining specific data.

Need for specificity in questions: Several emphasised the need for highly specific questions to receive the desired AI responses. In some cases, questions had to be very precise to obtain relevant information.

Summary: *Students faced challenges in understanding and responding to AI, noted grammatical and content errors, had difficulties in citing sources, found limited usefulness for specific cases, and highlighted the need for highly specific questions.*

6. How do you think artificial intelligence has influenced the quality and innovation of your final product (professional manual or short film)?

Rapid acquisition of important information for a better product: Many emphasised that using AI enabled the quick acquisition of essential information, positively impacting the quality of the final product. AI proved to be an efficient source of information.

Increase in ideas and material for manuals: In creating professional manuals, several respondents observed that AI contributed more ideas and material, ultimately improving the quality of the manuals.

Impact on ideas, upgrades, and information search: Respondents stressed that AI positively influenced ideas, upgraded them, and facilitated quick information retrieval. This contributed to higher product quality.

Diverse opinions on the impact on films: Opinions on the impact of AI on short films varied. Some believed AI had a significant impact on quality, while others thought the film would be the same without AI, as it was entirely the result of their own ideas.

Impact on writing style and organisation: Concerns were raised about a uniform (mechanical) writing style contributed by AI, affecting the diversity of the final product.

Summary: The use of AI allowed for the rapid acquisition of important information, increased ideas and material for professional manuals, positively influenced ideas, upgrades, and information search for a better final product. However, opinions on the impact of AI on short films differed, and a uniform writing style contributed by AI raised concerns about the diversity of the final product.

Likert Scale Questions (1 to 5):

7. Rate the extent to which you think the use of artificial intelligence contributed to the innovation of your final product. From 1 (did not contribute at all) to 5 (contributed completely).

Contribution of AI to the innovation of the final product	Number of decisions	%
1. Did not contribute at all	2	5.6
2. Contributed a little	6	16.7
3. Contributed moderately	9	25.0
4. Contributed significantly	12	33.3
5. Contributed very significantly	7	19.4

Comment: Over 77% of students believe that the use of AI contributed to the innovation of the final product, with 19.4% indicating a very significant contribution. Only 5.6% of students believed there was no positive effect.

8. To what extent do you think that the use of artificial intelligence has facilitated your understanding and solving of challenges in media production? Rate from 1 (very low) to 5 (very high).

Contribution of AI to the facilitation of understanding and solving challenges	Number of decisions	%
1 did not facilitate at all	0	-
2 slightly facilitated	5	13.9
3 moderately facilitated	10	27.8
4 facilitated considerably	13	36.1
5 facilitated a lot	8	22.2

Summary: All students believe that AI has at least slightly facilitated their understanding and solving of challenges in media production. Of these, 13.9% feel it helped only a little, while 58.3% found it considerably or very helpful.

9. How would you rate the satisfaction level with the results of the project for which artificial intelligence was used?

Satisfaction with project results using AI	Number of decisions	%
1 very dissatisfied	1	2.8
2 dissatisfied	0	0
3 neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	2	5.6
4 satisfied	28	77.7
5 very satisfied	5	13.9

Summary: A total of 91.6% of students are satisfied or very satisfied with the results of the project that involved the use of AI, while less than 8% are dissatisfied or undecided.

10. Rank the following elements based on how much you think they contributed to the success of the project (1 least important, 5 most important):

- 5. Previous project experiences
- 4. Effective group composition
- 3. Use of artificial intelligence
- 2. Clear instructions
- 1. Analysis of similar cases from domestic and foreign practices

Summary: Students rated previous project experiences and effective group composition as the most significant contributors to the project's success, with AI ranking third.

11. In your opinion, which of the following aspects of artificial intelligence usage would be most beneficial to your fellow students in media production? (1 least useful, 5 most useful)

- 5. Data acquisition
- 4. Communication
- 3. Instructions for specific tasks
- 2. Research of sources
- 1. Data processing

Summary: Students believe that AI will be most beneficial in data acquisition.

12. Rank the following statements based on how much you agree with them regarding the impact of artificial intelligence on project success (1 least important, 5 most important):

- 5. Artificial intelligence has facilitated solving challenges in creating professional manuals and short films.
- 4. Artificial intelligence has improved organisational processes in media production.
- 3. Artificial intelligence has increased the project's innovativeness.
- 2. Today, it's possible to make a very good film with the help of AI.
- 1. Without artificial intelligence, we wouldn't be able to prepare a good manual.

Summary: According to students, AI has facilitated solving challenges in creating materials, but they disagree that without AI, they wouldn't be able to prepare a good manual.

Discussion

In the discussion, summaries and analysis of results, as well as an evaluation of the validity of our hypotheses, are presented.

The research results indicate that artificial intelligence positively influences the process of creating materials, especially professional manuals. Students report time savings, organisational assistance, and increased efficiency. A significant 94.4% of students believe that the inclusion of artificial intelligence facilitates the process of creating professional manuals and short films. 86.1% of students estimate that, with the help of artificial intelligence, less time was spent preparing a professional manual compared to the traditional approach. Information was more accessible, and ideas emerged more quickly. However, opinions differ regarding the utility of artificial intelligence in creating short films, for which some perceive benefits, while others believe that the creative process depends more on human imagination.

Opinions are also divided regarding the assistance of artificial intelligence in organising and managing media projects. 55.5% of students believe that artificial intelligence has helped them in better organising and managing media projects. 27.8% think there was no such assistance, and 16.7% either did not know or preferred not to answer.

Students also mentioned challenges in using artificial intelligence, such as understanding and responding, grammatical and content errors, and limited applicability to specific cases.

Hypothesis 1: Students using ChatGPT in creating a professional manual will achieve better results in less time compared to those not using this tool. Hypothesis 5 is confirmed.

Hypothesis 2: Students using ChatGPT in creating an audiovisual product will produce a more creative product than those without ChatGPT. Students' opinions mostly do not confirm this hypothesis, especially concerning films, so Hypothesis 6 does not apply to the majority of students.

Conclusion

With the introduction of the widely useful and freely available product based on artificial intelligence, ChatGPT, which became generally available in 2023, including in the educational system, we decided to conduct a study to identify some basic characteristics, possibilities, and potential problems of using ChatGPT in planning and implementing the study process.

Before starting the research, we reviewed the state of education by examining scientific and professional sources and directions. This review revealed that artificial intelligence has great potential in addressing key challenges in education, innovating teaching, and accelerating progress toward sustainable development goals. However, there are also numerous dilemmas and objections to the rapid introduction of artificial intelligence into education.

In the study, when using ChatGPT, we focused mainly on those functions crucial for data acquisition and processing in planning and implementing multimedia production.

At the beginning of the research, we posed the research question: What is the impact of artificial intelligence (ChatGPT) on the success of students in creating materials: professional manuals and short films?

According to the survey, 94.4% of students believe that ChatGPT positively influences the process of creating materials, especially professional manuals, as information was more accessible, and ideas emerged more quickly. However, opinions differ concerning the utility of artificial intelligence in creating scenarios for short films, regarding which some perceive benefits, while others believe that the creative process depends more on human imagination. Opinions are also divided regarding the assistance of artificial intelligence in organising and managing media projects, as only 55.5% of students

believe that artificial intelligence has helped them in better organising and managing media projects.

With the study, we confirmed Hypothesis 1, while Hypothesis 2 does not apply to the majority of students, as their opinions mostly do not confirm this hypothesis, especially concerning films.

To encourage teachers to introduce ChatGPT into the study process, a student's thought is provided: "By using ChatGPT, I am much more motivated for studying and work since I know where to get all the necessary information for any content. I know that with the help of AI, I will complete a better task, so I start working with more enthusiasm."

With our research, we aim to make a modest contribution to understanding the introduction of ChatGPT into the study process. Simultaneously, we provide useful suggestions for planning the subject in the next academic year and generally for the activities of the faculty and its vision and strategy for introducing AI.

The entire research is presented in the research project report. (Zakrajšek. 2024)

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NOTE: In the preparation and execution of the research, as well as in the preparation of the final report and article, we practically utilised the assistance of ChatGPT in all stages.

Resources

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